

Table S2. Low- and high-frequency magnetic susceptibility of Australasian tektites from South China. Note that some Muong Nong-type tektites and splash-form tektites exhibit negative values of $\chi_{fd}\%$ (red), which may be caused by noise disturbances due to the extremely low contents of ferromagnetic materials (e.g., superparamagnetic/single domain threshold grains) in those subsamples of tektites.

Sample ID	Type	$\chi_{fr} (10^{-9} \text{ SI})$	$\chi_{hf} (10^{-9} \text{ SI})$	$\chi_{fd}\%$
MNL-1	Muong Nong-type	23.56	21.73	0.08
MNL-2	Muong Nong-type	52.24	53.95	-0.03
MNL-3	Muong Nong-type	51.37	53.64	-0.04
MNL-4	Muong Nong-type	50.58	51.02	-0.01
MNL-5	Muong Nong-type	52.37	52.77	-0.01
MNL-6	Muong Nong-type	48.75	50.57	-0.04
HN2-1	Muong Nong-type	54.66	55.75	-0.02
HN2-2	Muong Nong-type	46.31	42.39	0.08
HN2-3	Muong Nong-type	49.15	49.13	0.00
HN2-4	Muong Nong-type	50.64	50.21	0.01
HN5-1	Muong Nong-type	59.57	58.84	0.01
HN5-2	Muong Nong-type	50.65	47.31	0.07
HN5-3	Muong Nong-type	46.74	50.45	-0.08
HN5-4	Muong Nong-type	43.34	44.88	-0.04
HN5-5	Muong Nong-type	38.17	38.70	-0.01
HN5-6	Muong Nong-type	45.98	43.57	0.05
HN7-1	Muong Nong-type	56.66	54.26	0.04
HN7-2	Muong Nong-type	61.38	60.90	0.01
HN7-3	Muong Nong-type	33.28	32.49	0.02
HN7-4	Muong Nong-type	57.39	55.07	0.04
HN8-1	Muong Nong-type	55.78	57.81	-0.04
HN8-2	Muong Nong-type	46.47	46.22	0.01
HN8-3	Muong Nong-type	48.33	48.15	0.00
HN8-4	Muong Nong-type	38.44	37.79	0.02
HN9-1	Muong Nong-type	50.09	45.64	0.09
HN9-2	Muong Nong-type	55.29	54.87	0.01
HN9-3	Muong Nong-type	55.74	57.06	-0.02
HN9-4	Muong Nong-type	57.84	54.77	0.05

HN9-5	Muong Nong-type	35.09	39.57	-0.13
HN10-A1	Muong Nong-type	51.40	52.01	-0.01
HN10-A2	Muong Nong-type	51.20	47.73	0.07
HN10-A3	Muong Nong-type	52.06	46.93	0.10
HN10-A4	Muong Nong-type	31.68	22.78	0.28
HN10-A5	Muong Nong-type	53.19	48.94	0.08
HN10-B1	Muong Nong-type	54.78	52.69	0.04
HN10-B2	Muong Nong-type	45.29	42.16	0.07
HN10-B3	Muong Nong-type	44.09	48.98	-0.11
HN10-B4	Muong Nong-type	46.52	45.45	0.02
HN10-B5	Muong Nong-type	41.84	44.38	-0.06
HN11-A1	Muong Nong-type	39.92	38.39	0.04
HN11-A2	Muong Nong-type	46.31	44.72	0.03
HN11-A3	Muong Nong-type	45.25	45.53	-0.01
HN11-A4	Muong Nong-type	45.17	46.25	-0.02
HN11-A5	Muong Nong-type	47.72	47.64	0.00
HN11-A6	Muong Nong-type	54.60	55.48	-0.02
HN11-B2	Muong Nong-type	21.38	22.24	-0.04
HN11-B3	Muong Nong-type	28.78	33.08	-0.15
HN11-B4	Muong Nong-type	33.29	28.91	0.13
HN11-B5	Muong Nong-type	35.61	36.02	-0.01
HN11-B6	Muong Nong-type	41.40	40.26	0.03
HN12-1	Muong Nong-type	50.55	51.75	-0.02
HN12-2	Muong Nong-type	58.07	57.03	0.02
HN12-3	Muong Nong-type	55.14	53.33	0.03
HN13-1	Muong Nong-type	66.15	62.99	0.05
HN13-2	Muong Nong-type	65.88	61.84	0.06
HN13-3	Muong Nong-type	65.70	64.01	0.03
HN13-4	Muong Nong-type	41.68	42.40	-0.02
HN13-5	Muong Nong-type	62.56	61.98	0.01
HN14-1	Muong Nong-type	54.34	53.12	0.02
HN14-2	Muong Nong-type	26.34	27.65	-0.05
DTS6-1	Splash-form	65.36	63.34	0.03
DTS6-3	Splash-form	60.82	59.14	0.03
GPZ-2	Splash-form	77.71	75.64	0.03
DTS6-2	Splash-form	60.35	58.47	0.03

DT-2-2	Splash-form	80.44	78.65	0.02
BSP	Splash-form	75.59	77.48	-0.02
DT-1	Splash-form	53.11	52.64	0.01
GC-2	Splash-form	81.61	79.22	0.03
EC	Splash-form	81.56	78.96	0.03
HKS1E-1	Splash-form	71.00	68.82	0.03
HNS1E-4	Splash-form	74.81	72.32	0.03
HNWC-1	Splash-form	73.65	72.47	0.02
LZ-2	Splash-form	58.72	64.57	-0.10
HKS1-1	Splash-form	71.40	69.05	0.03
LZS1-1	Splash-form	78.67	74.93	0.05
LZS2-1	Splash-form	81.80	79.00	0.03
LZS2-2	Splash-form	49.25	48.12	0.02
LZS1-2	Splash-form	82.61	79.78	0.03
HNWC-1-2	Splash-form	51.72	54.27	-0.05
LZS4B	Splash-form	67.07	69.62	-0.04
LZ-5	Splash-form	76.31	74.13	0.03
GDWC-2-1	Splash-form	85.30	82.57	0.03
GDWC-2-2	Splash-form	82.86	80.25	0.03
GDWC-D-1	Splash-form	88.78	85.66	0.04
GDWC-D-2	Splash-form	86.47	82.54	0.05
GDWC-S1-1	Splash-form	88.80	85.70	0.03
GDMM-2-2	Splash-form	85.62	83.32	0.03
WSD-R1	Splash-form	83.22	79.96	0.04
WSD-R3	Splash-form	81.38	79.62	0.02
WSD-2	Splash-form	80.80	77.94	0.04
WSD-3	Splash-form	72.41	71.21	0.02
WC-3	Splash-form	83.93	80.80	0.04
GXYL-3	Splash-form	78.93	76.60	0.03
ZJS4-2	Splash-form	76.71	74.47	0.03
GXYL-S1	Splash-form	82.14	79.92	0.03
ZJS1	Splash-form	87.12	84.13	0.03
ZJS3	Splash-form	51.92	52.67	-0.01
ZJS5	Splash-form	64.51	64.04	0.01
YL-2	Splash-form	52.47	50.46	0.04
ZJS6	Splash-form	35.43	35.02	0.01

ZJS6-1	Splash-form	106.15	105.60	0.01
ZJS7	Splash-form	53.95	50.27	0.07
ZJS8	Splash-form	86.31	83.70	0.03
ZWC-4	Splash-form	75.21	73.46	0.02
ZWC-5	Splash-form	71.27	69.77	0.02
ZJZW	Splash-form	48.34	50.88	-0.05
GC-AF	Splash-form	90.38	80.15	0.11
ZWC-AF	Splash-form	74.46	53.15	0.29
HNWN-S3-AF	Splash-form	91.49	84.02	0.08
GDLZ-2-AF	Splash-form	84.73	77.00	0.09
GDLZ-2-2-AF	Splash-form	89.00	77.11	0.13
WSD-AF	Splash-form	69.92	59.87	0.14
GJDT-AF	Splash-form	89.73	83.74	0.07
GC-IRM	Splash-form	91.25	80.76	0.11
ZWC-IRM	Splash-form	71.39	65.47	0.08
HNWN-S3-IRM	Splash-form	81.62	76.24	0.07
GDLZ-2-IRM	Splash-form	90.87	79.14	0.13
GDLZ-2-2-IRM	Splash-form	91.18	82.35	0.10
WSD-IRM	Splash-form	74.88	39.47	0.47
GJDT-IRM	Splash-form	85.88	80.10	0.07
GXYL-2-IRM	Splash-form	100.07	84.98	0.15
WSD-L	Splash-form	74.89	57.62	0.23
WSD-2-L	Splash-form	74.34	54.05	0.27
ZWC-L	Splash-form	74.26	35.27	0.53
HNDF-S1-L	Splash-form	84.23	72.13	0.14
BSP-L	Splash-form	84.23	60.63	0.28
ZJDT-L	Splash-form	90.64	76.43	0.16
GDLZ-2-L	Splash-form	91.08	58.22	0.36
GXYL-3-L	Splash-form	82.70	66.72	0.19